

REHABILITATION IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INTEGRATION AND INCLUSION

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Annotation: This article is about inclusive education, inclusive classrooms value all students as capable learners and contributors to society. It focuses on understanding their differences, appreciating their individual similarities and differences, and thus reading and learning.

Key words: inclusive, integrated education, education, teaching, classroom, pedagogy.

Аннотация: Эта статья посвящена инклюзивному образованию, инклюзивным классам, в которых все учащиеся ценятся как способные ученики и вносят свой вклад в общество. Они сосредоточены на понимании их различий, оценке их индивидуальных сходств и различий, а значит, на чтении и обучении.

Ключевые слова: инклюзивное, интегрированное образование, воспитание, обучение, класс, педагогика

The terms 'inclusive' and 'integrated' used synonymously. However, philosophically, there is a huge difference between these concepts. Placing a child with disabilities in a normal environment is the first step towards inclusion. The inclusion of children with disabilities in mainstream education referred to as "inclusive" or "integrative" education. To define the term "integration", let us turn to the dictionary "Pedagogical Dictionary" by G.M. Kaidasparov, who defined this concept? It considers "integration of groups" and "regulation of relations between individuals in a group" and emphasizes that integration can be implemented only by creating humane relations and positive public opinion in this group. In recent years, serious attention paid to the education of children with disabilities in general education on an equal basis with all their peers, and inclusive education has been widely publicized through the media. In this regard, parents have expressed a desire to educate their children in integrated and inclusive groups and classes in the general education system. Integrated education is the process of a child with special needs attending school, which focuses on the problem of getting the child to school. In

integrated education, the child seen as a problem. This educational system has the following forms: Physical integration.

This form of integration aims at reducing the physical difference between disabled and handicapped children. A special department or class for disabled children organized next to the regular school. Functional integration. This form aims to reduce functional problems between disabled and non-disabled children. Social integration. This form of integration aims to reduce social problems and supports interaction between disabled and non-disabled children. For example, community integration. Effective inclusion ensures inclusive education for all students regardless of ability, race, language ability, economic, ethnic, cultural and religious beliefs, gender, learning style, religious beliefs, family structure, and sexual orientation. Inclusive programs provide all students with access to education. Stimulating, engaging, and adaptive curriculum that helps them succeed in society. (Fisher and Frey, 2001; Roach, Salisbury and McGregor, 2002). Effective inclusion is a team effort; It involves a collaborative community of educators and other professionals, students, families, and community organizations (Hunt, Soto, Meyer, & Dering, 2003; Jackson, Rindek, & Billingsley, 2000). Inclusion aims to create a community of learners that is responsive to the needs of students in general education classrooms (Sepon-Shevin, 2003). People cooperate and work together and create community. They constantly interact, share resources, commitments, and experiences, and work together to solve certain problems for the benefit of students (Hunt et al., 2000; Ruder, 2000). Public education departments support, provide time and resources to work together to restructure (re-adapt) programs to meet the needs of learners.

The study found that those who were included in special education classes at a university school had more positive outcomes in the area of experience than participants included in a regular classroom. Selection for inclusive education therefore requires precision, as some types of education are more effective others. This means that full inclusion of children with disabilities in education leads to negative situations. A number of accommodation methods used to ensure the right to necessary education. The results of both studies confirm that educating children with disabilities in regular classrooms is morally impossible for the realization of an individual's right to education. Inclusive education ensures that children with special needs receive education and upbringing on equal rights with children with normal development. This is why it is important.

The “Universal Declaration of Human Rights” adopted by the UN in 1948 specifically recognized that “Education is a fundamental and inalienable right of every human being”. Since the “Universal Declaration of Human Rights” guarantees the rights and freedoms of all human beings, established that all the provisions of this Declaration also apply to people with special needs. In order to further strengthen and guarantee the rights of persons with disabilities, the UN adopted the Declaration on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in 1975. This Declaration states: “The right to respect for the person of persons with disabilities is available to them from birth. Irrespective of the origin, nature and degree of the disability, a citizen has the same rights as his or her peers, and at the same time, they are entitled to live in dignity to the fullest extent possible. “Schools should accept all children, regardless of their physical, mental, social, emotional, linguistic or other disabilities. This includes children with mental and physical disabilities, homeless children, nomadic children, children from ethnically or culturally disadvantaged families.” The Salamanca Declaration and Plan of Action on Inclusive Education for Children with Special Needs in General Education emphasizes that every child has different needs from others and that every child has the right to go to a school close to his or her place of residence. Similarly, to protect the rights of children, the UN adopted the “Convention on the Rights of the Child” in 1989. “The Convention on the Rights of the Child” is an international human rights treaty designed to protect the rights of children around the world. It ratified by almost every country in the world. The 191 countries that have ratified the Convention have voluntarily pledged to implement the provisions of the “Convention on the Rights of the Child” through administrative legislation, courts and other measures.

The Convention on the Rights of the Child is comprehensive and multifaceted and is the only Convention that provides civil, political, economic, social and cultural aspects of human rights for all children. This convention is strictly enforced. “Continuity of education is the key to the new global economy. “Education is fundamental to development, social progress and human freedom.” In many countries, education in general education schools is included in the plan of scientific and practical state policy in order to develop compensatory possibilities of high achievable development of children with special needs and full social integration. According to L.S. Vygotsky, the task of educating a disabled child is to compensate for the child's shortcomings and ensure his/her integration into life, and for this purpose, it is necessary to create such an educational system in the process of educating a child with special

needs. Let him/her develop in all respects. That is, L.S. Vygotsky recognized the creation of an educational system that harmonizes general and special education/education of children in need of special help in the system of general education. The policy of development of integrated (inclusive) education in Uzbekistan based on the following principles: recognition of integrated (inclusive) education as an important factor of sustainable development. Rehabilitation, adaptation and integration of children with disabilities integration of all strategic forces, state and non-state structures, the public in order to preserve and develop integrated (inclusive) education; accessibility of integrated (inclusive) education for all, adaptation of the educational system to the needs of children with disabilities. Integration of all strategic forces, state and non-state structures, and the public in order to maintain and develop integrated (inclusive) education; accessibility of integrated (inclusive) education for all, adaptation of the educational system to the needs of children with disabilities. Specialists of the psychological-medical-pedagogical commission entrusted with the task of studying and diagnosing the mental and physical condition of the child, and comprehensive examination of the child, recommendations given on the education of children and the determination of appropriate educational conditions for them.

Thus, for the effective inclusion of a child with special needs in the sphere of general education it is necessary: from an early age to begin corrective measures, allowing achieving positive results in the development of the child, medical-psychological-pedagogical for each child engaged in general education organization of education, i.e. constant accompaniment of specialists. Based on the mental and physical development and educational needs, it is necessary to ensure the selection of the necessary forms of upbringing and education for each child. Any form of involvement of the child in the educational system should be simple and useful for him/her and at the same time should not interfere with the quality education of his/her peers developing in the conditions of inclusive education.

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